

Data Management Plan of the Research Project "Improvements on Aeropalinological Monitoring (AVIONETA)" (PID2024-157581OB-I00)

Version 1

Description

This data management plan (DMP) is contextualised within the framework of Project PID2024-157581OB-I00, funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the ERDF, EU.

The research project, entitled 'Improvements on Aeropalinological Monitoring (AVIONETA)', will run from 1 September 2025 to 31 August 2028, with the participation of the Technical University of Cartagena and the University of Castilla-La Mancha (Spain). The project aims to increase the accuracy of sampling and bioaerosol (pollen) determination methods through innovative environmental DNA analysis techniques and automatic devices. This DMP is intended to be a useful tool for managing research data derived from this research activity, which is publicly funded by the State Research Agency.

Funder

10.13039/501100011033

Grant

PID2024

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Castile-La Mancha, Polytechnic University of Cartagena

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data Management Plan of the Research Project "Improvements on Aeropalinological Monitoring (AVIONETA)" (PID2024-157581OB-I00)

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Polytechnic University of Cartagena

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: 10.13039/501100011033

Grants: PID2024

Project: [PID2024-157581OB-I00](#)

3. License

License: [AFL-3.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Pollen grain concentrations obtained by the Hirst Method (EN 16868:2019)

The standardised method for reporting pollen concentrations according to EN 16868:2019 requires a Hirst-type trap that samples the ambient air containing pollen grains. The pollen grains are adhered to a Mellinex tape that requires laboratory treatment and subsequent reading under an optical microscope. This reading requires personnel who are experts in identifying pollen types. Therefore, the data generated by this method is research data under intellectual property rights.

Template: [AQUASERV | generic | template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Types of data and usage

1.1.1 Data Types

I will compile pollen concentrations (pollen grains/m³) in a spreadsheet (CSV). The tabular measurements will be the pollen grain concentrations after reading the pollen grains collected on a Mellinex tape with an optical microscope (standard EN 16868:2019).

1.1.2 Data Creation

The data will be the result of field collection and subsequent reading with optical microscopy by an expert.

1.1.3 Published Data Re-use

No

All data of this type will be created in the context of the project PID2024-157581OB-I00 funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF, EU.

1.1.4 Data size

it is estimated to be less than 1 GB.

2 FAIR Data Publication

2.1 Findable

2.1.1 Data Publication Repository

Zenodo or the repository recommended by the Learning and Research Resource Centre of the participating universities will be used to ensure the principles of Open Science and FAIR data.

2.1.2 Metadata collection

CERIF (Common European Research Information Format)

I will collect the following information in a spreadsheet: the names and ORCID IDs of all the people involved in the work, the coordinates of my sampling field work, the name of service provider where I did the work, the dates of the sample collection and the subsequent sample and data processing.

I will include these information in the metadata form when I publish my data on Zenodo or the repository of my university.

I will ask the TA service provider for the types/names and IDs of all the instruments and devices I will use.

I will create a README to describe each file in my data set.

I will also ask the TA service provider for the URL/DOI of their protocols that I followed and will record this in my README.

2.2 Accessible

2.2.1 Repository

2.2.1.1 Open Access Data Repositories

Yes

Zenodo and the repository of my (our) university is public.

2.2.1.2 Persistent URLs and identifiers

Zenodo and my (our) university assign a DOI to each validated and uploaded database.

2.2.2 Research Data

2.2.2.1 Licence

The licence will be CC-BY 4.0.

2.2.2.2 Data Publication Embargo

Yes

The deposited data will be subject to an embargo period corresponding to the time until publication through the usual channels of dissemination in scientific journals. This is to protect the intellectual property of the research team that generated the data. The principal investigators of the project will be responsible for lifting the embargo: Luis Negral (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8384-9541>) and Rosa Pérez-Badia (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2471-4388>).

2.2.2.3 Restricted Data Usage

Yes

The access restrictions will remain in place until the end of the embargo period. Once open, the data will be accessed via the repository.

2.2.2.4 Unpublished Data

No

Null results will also be reported.

2.3 Interoperable

2.3.1 Open Data Formats

Yes

I will convert my MS Excel files to CSV before I publish them, so they are in an open format.

2.3.2 Vocabularies and Ontologies

I will use NCBI taxonomy for all taxon names, and will use their recommended IDs for the names.

2.4 Re-useable (and reproducible)

2.4.1 Methods and Protocols

Yes

The methods will be published in papers and the repository of my (our) university.

3 Other issues

Pollen grain concentrations obtained by DNA Methods

Environmental DNA (eDNA) analysis, particularly eDNA metabarcoding, enables the extraction and sequencing of genetic material from environmental samples to identify the organisms present. In the context of the AVIONETA project, the purpose of this dataset is to characterise the aerobiological content of pollen grains using eDNA metabarcoding analysis.

Template: [AQUASERV | generic | template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Types of data and usage

1.1.1 Data Types

I will compile pollen concentrations (pollen grains/m³) in a spreadsheet (CSV). The tabular measurements will be the pollen grain concentrations after reading the pollen grains collected on a glass fiber filter with DNA techniques.

1.1.2 Data Creation

The data will be the result of field collection of the Total Suspended Particulate (TSP) on filters and subsequent DNA quantification.

1.1.3 Published Data Re-use

No

All data of this type will be created in the context of the project PID2024-157581OB-I00 funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF, EU.

1.1.4 Data size

it is estimated to be less than 2 GB.

2 FAIR Data Publication

2.1 Findable

2.1.1 Data Publication Repository

Zenodo or the repository recommended by the Learning and Research Resource Centre of the participating universities will be used to ensure the principles of Open Science and FAIR data.

2.1.2 Metadata collection

CERIF (Common European Research Information Format)

I will collect the following information in a spreadsheet: the names and ORCID IDs of all the people involved in the work, the coordinates of my sampling field work, the name of service provider where I did the work, the dates of the sample collection and the subsequent sample and data processing.

I will include these information in the metadata form when I publish my data on Zenodo or the repository of my university.

I will ask the TA service provider for the types/names and IDs of all the instruments and devices I will use.

I will create a README to describe each file in my data set.

I will also ask the TA service provider for the URL/DOI of their protocols that I followed and will record this in my README.

2.2 Accessible

2.2.1 Repository

2.2.1.1 Open Access Data Repositories

Yes

Zenodo and the repository of my (our) university is public.

2.2.1.2 Persistent URLs and identifiers

Zenodo and my (our) university assign a DOI to each validated and uploaded database.

2.2.2 Research Data

2.2.2.1 Licence

The licence will be CC-BY 4.0.

2.2.2.2 Data Publication Embargo

Yes

The deposited data will be subject to an embargo period corresponding to the time until publication through the usual channels of dissemination in scientific journals. This is to protect the intellectual property of the research team that generated the data. The principal investigators of the project will be responsible for lifting the embargo: Luis Negral (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8384-9541>) and Rosa Pérez-Badia (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2471-4388>).

2.2.2.3 Restricted Data Usage

Yes

The access restrictions will remain in place until the end of the embargo period. Once open, the data will be accessed via the repository.

2.2.2.4 Unpublished Data

No

Null results will also be reported.

2.3 Interoperable

2.3.1 Open Data Formats

Yes

I will convert my MS Excel files to CSV before I publish them, so they are in an open format.

2.3.2 Vocabularies and Ontologies

I will use NCBI taxonomy for all taxon names, and will use their recommended IDs for the names.

2.4 Re-useable (and reproducible)

2.4.1 Methods and Protocols

Yes

The methods will be published in papers and the repository of my (our) university.

3 Other issues

Pollen grain concentrations by real-time data based on image or holographic recognition

The emerging aerobiological techniques of automatic monitoring provide high resolution temporal information, which substantially improves the understanding of the challenges related to the study of bioaerosols.

In the context of the AVIONETA project, this dataset presents the results of the Swisens Poleno Mars equipment designed by for the observation and exhaustive classification of aerosols from orthogonal holography using lasers of different wavelengths to produce back dispersion and fluorescence that identify particles.

Template: [AQUASERV | generic | template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Types of data and usage

1.1.1 Data Types

I will compile pollen concentrations (pollen grains/m³) in a spreadsheet (CSV). The tabular measurements will be the pollen grain concentrations as the automatic equipment Swisens Poleno Mars (digital holography) reports during the sampling campaigns.

1.1.2 Data Creation

The data will be the result of the field implementation of the automatic equipment Swisens Poleno Mars.

1.1.3 Published Data Re-use

No

All data of this type will be created in the context of the project PID2024-157581OB-I00 funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF, EU.

1.1.4 Data size

it is estimated to be less than 5 GB.

2 FAIR Data Publication

2.1 Findable

2.1.1 Data Publication Repository

Zenodo or the repository recommended by the Learning and Research Resource Centre of the participating universities will be used to ensure the principles of Open Science and FAIR data.

2.1.2 Metadata collection

CERIF (Common European Research Information Format)

I will collect the following information in a spreadsheet: the names and ORCID IDs of all the people involved in the work, the coordinates of my sampling field work, the name of service provider where I did the work, the dates of the sample collection and the subsequent sample and data processing.

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I will also ask the TA service provider for the URL/DOI of their protocols that I followed and will record this in my README.

2.2 Accessible

2.2.1 Repository

2.2.1.1 Open Access Data Repositories

Yes

Zenodo and the repository of my (our) university is public.

2.2.1.2 Persistent URLs and identifiers

Zenodo and my (our) university assign a DOI to each validated and uploaded database.

2.2.2 Research Data

2.2.2.1 Licence

The licence will be CC-BY 4.0.

2.2.2.2 Data Publication Embargo

No

The data will be deposited as primary taxa every six months, following a preliminary and subjective review of the reported pollen categories.

2.2.2.3 Restricted Data Usage

Yes

The access restrictions will remain in place until the end of the embargo period. Once open, the data will be accessed via the repository.

Restrictions on reuse will come from recognition of public funding (Project PID2024-157581OB-I00 funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF, EU) and the intellectual property of the researchers responsible for processing the data generated by the device.

2.2.2.4 Unpublished Data

No

Null results will also be reported.

2.3 Interoperable

2.3.1 Open Data Formats

Yes

I will convert my MS Excel files to CSV before I publish them, so they are in an open format.

2.3.2 Vocabularies and Ontologies

I will use NCBI taxonomy for all taxon names, and will use their recommended IDs for the names.

2.4 Re-useable (and reproducible)

2.4.1 Methods and Protocols

Yes

The methods will be published in papers and the repository of my (our) university.

3 Other issues

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